

Digital Learning in Secondary Schools of Kanpur: Some Issues

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Abstract

The rapid shift to online education due to global events has highlighted both the potential and limitations of digital learning environments. While online teaching and learning offer increased accessibility and flexibility, personalized learning, global connectivity, future readiness, cost effectiveness, parental involvement, they also present unique challenges for educators and students alike. This paper examines the key obstacles faced in online education, particularly in Kanpur. By analyzing these issues, present research aims to provide insights for improving the effectiveness of online teaching and learning practices. The results revealed that Compared to aided schools, non-aided schools seem to be more strengthened with resources like smart classrooms, internet speed facilities, and availability of computers. Rural schools are least empowered with these resources. It also disclosed the fact that the teachers, students and even parents of Non-aided schools have shown more positive attitudes towards online teaching-learning than those of aided and rural schools. The other factors like Technological literacy, Access to technology, Learning Style, Support system, Motivation, Infrastructure, and Communication, which affects the adaptability towards the change from traditional to online is found high in Urban Schools and non-aided schools in comparison to Aided and Rural Schools. School management of non-aided schools were providing greater facilities in comparison to those of aided schools. Parents of non-aided schools were more aware, alert and active, and providing greater facilities than that of aided and rural schools. Findings from this research can influence educators, institutions, and policymakers to enhance the quality of digital education, specially in aided schools, and in rural areas, where it is needed more. As challenges evolve and new technologies emerge, research can help schools and educators adapt and thrive in the digital learning landscape.

Keywords Online Teaching, Digital Divide Secondary Schools.

Introduction

Online teaching-learning has become increasingly crucial for secondary education due to its ability to provide flexible, accessible, and personalized learning experiences. As it provides education to all students in remote areas and or those with physical limitations with a wider range of educational materials and expert knowledge, it allows students to learn at their own pace (Kulal and Nayak, 2020) and accommodates various learning styles. Online learning also prepares students for a technology-driven world (Garg, et al 2010; Kumar, 2013), enhancing their digital skills. In the last pandemic time, online teaching ensured continuing learning during worldwide disruption (Jindel et al., 2022; Sobaih et al., 2022). It exposes students to diverse perspectives and cultures through virtual collaborations as it also introduces online collaboration tools used in higher education (Rastogi, 2019). It facilitates tailored instruction and immediate feedback through adaptive technologies (Gautam et al.,2022). Online teaching -learning also allows parents to more easily monitor their child's education. It can reduce expenses related to physical infrastructure and materials. By integrating online teaching-learning, secondary schools can better prepare students for the challenges and opportunities of the 21st century, ensuring they develop the skills necessary for success in an increasingly digital world (Suri,2021).

Objective of study

1. To explore the resources available in schools for online teaching- learning
2. To study the attitudes of Stakeholders towards change from traditional to online teaching-learning methodology.
3. To study the factors affecting the adaptability towards the change.

4. To study the role of management and parents in providing facilities to improve teaching-learning.
5. To compare the government-aided and non-aided schools and Rural and Urban Schools regarding resources, attitudes of different stakeholders, providing facilities by management and parents, and other factors affecting adaptability towards online teaching-learning.

Review of Literature

Broadbent, et al. (2015) investigated the relationship between self-regulated learning strategies and academic achievement in online higher education and highlighted the importance of time management, goal-setting, and self-monitoring for successful online learning outcomes. Borup et al. (2014) revealed in their research regarding teacher-student interactions in online learning, that regular communication and feedback, (Songkrama et al., 2015) significantly enhance students' performance. Hodges et al. (2020) emphasized the need for proper planning, course design, and online support for effective online education (Nguyen, 2015). The students in interactive distance education environment, perform comparably to those in traditional classrooms (Cavanaugh et al., 2004). Though there are major challenges (Chugh et al., 2017) in the way such as, digital-divide, lack of infrastructure, poor internet connectivity, limited access to technology etc. (Jena, 2020; Soni, 2020; Azeez and Vanitha, 2020; Garg and Sengupta, 2021). Regional disparity in online education is the significant challenge (Shraim, et al., 2010) and need more efforts to ensure equitable access (Goyal, 2020; Saxena et al., 2020; Garg and Sen Gupta, 2021). An additional training for teachers is required for conducting effective online classes (Kumari and Rao, 2020; Chaudhary and Priyadarshini, 2021). The Ministry of Human Resource Development's report on "Digital Education in India" outlines the various initiatives taken by the Indian government to promote online education. The report includes the launch of platforms like DIKSHA, SWAYAM, and PM eVIDYA to support online learning (MHRD, 2020). Challenges and Opportunities" by the National Council of Educational Research and Training provides insights into the implementation of online education and the support mechanism needed to enhance its effectiveness (NCERT, 2021).

Main Text Sampling

The research was conducted in government-aided and Non-aided secondary schools of Kanpur and Kanpur Dehat, which are under Uttar Pradesh Madhyamik Shiksha Parishad (UPMSP). A sample of 1000 respondents had been taken from all the stakeholders of the above-mentioned schools and data was collected through a self-made questionnaire *Challenges of online teaching-learning (QCOTL)* covering following areas.

- Resources available, necessary for online teaching-learning
2. Attitudes of Stakeholders toward online teaching-learning
 3. School management and Parents' role in providing resources
 4. Factors that affect adaptability
 - 4.1 Technological literacy
 - 4.2 Access to Technology
 - 4.3 Learning styles
 - 4.4 Support systems
 - 4.5 Motivation
 - 4.6 Infrastructure
 - 4.7 Communication

Analysis

1. To explore the resources available in schools for online teaching-learning.

Figure 1 clearly indicates that compared to aided schools, non-aided school seems to be more strengthened with resources regarding online teaching-learning. Rural schools are least empowered with these resources. As per the above figures regarding smart classrooms, Non-aided schools with 65% are the highest among all four groups, while rural schools are the lowest having only 10% of smart classes. For high-speed internet facilities, Non-aided schools with 50% are the highest among all followed by aided schools at 22%, urban schools at 22%, and rural schools with the lowest at 5%. The better status regarding the availability of computers in school is reported comparatively good as 72% in aided schools, 66.66% in aided and urban schools, and 40% in rural schools respectively. Thus, among all categories, rural schools are the lowest regarding resource availability in schools for online teaching-learning.

2. To study the attitudes of Stakeholders towards change from traditional to online teaching-learning methodology.

Figure- 2
The attitudes of Stakeholders towards change from traditional to online teaching- learning

Interpretation

In Figure-2, the attitudes of stakeholders toward the change from traditional to online teaching-learning indicates that the teachers of Non-aided schools are higher (86.66%) in this regard than that of the teachers of Aided (43.33%), Rural (33.33%) and Urban (50.00%) schools. The students are also showing the same trends for attitudes toward online teaching learning with (72.72%) of Non-aided schools, (21.21%) of Aided Schools, and (45.45%) of Urban Schools. Parents related to Non-aided schools have shown higher attitudes (83.33%) regarding the same than that of aided schools (13.33%), Rural schools (13.33%), and Urban schools (43.33%). Hence, the attitudes of all stakeholders regarding

the change from traditional to online teaching-learning have shown higher for Non-aided schools among all and have been gradually decreased with regard to Urban, Aided, and Rural schools.

3. To study the factors affecting the adaptability towards the change.

3.1 Technological Literacy

Differences among government-aided, non-aided, rural, and urban schools regarding the factor of 'Technological Literacy, affecting the adaptability towards the change

Figure3.1

The Technological Literacy Factor Affecting The Adaptability Toward The Change

Interpretation:

Figure 3.1 indicates that the factor, 'technological literacy' which affects the adaptability towards the change from traditional to online is found to be high in Non-Aided schools (71%), followed by Urban Schools (65%). Aided and Rural Schools have shown low technological literacy (34%) and (24%) respectively. Low technological literacy among stakeholders failed to motivate them to move towards online teaching-learning.

3.1 Access to Technology

Differences among government-aided, non-aided, rural, and urban schools regarding the factor of 'Access to Technology, affecting the adaptability towards the change

Figure: 3.2

The access to technology factor affecting the adaptability towards the change

Interpretation

Figure 3.2 indicates that the factor, 'access to technology' which affects the adaptability towards the change from traditional to online is found to be high in Non-Aided schools (68%), followed by Urban Schools (58%). Aided and Rural Schools have shown low access to technology with (41%) and (35%) respectively. The low level of access to technology among stakeholders failed to motivate them to move towards online teaching-learning (Soomro et.al., 2020).

3.3 Learning Style

Differences among government-aided, non-aided, rural, and urban schools regarding the factor of 'learning styles, affecting the adaptability towards the change

Figure: 3.3

The learning style factor affecting the adaptability towards the change

Figure: 3.3

The learning style factor affecting the adaptability towards the change

Interpretation

Figure 3.3 indicates that the factor, 'learning style' which affects the adaptability towards the change from traditional to online is found to be high in Non-Aided schools (79%), followed by Urban Schools (65%). Aided and Rural Schools have shown low scores on learning styles with (37%) and (32%) respectively.

3.4 Support System:

Differences among government-aided, non-aided, rural, and urban schools regarding the factor of 'support system', affecting the adaptability towards the change

Figure: 3.4

The Support system factor affecting the adaptability towards the change

Interpretation

In figure 3.4, it indicates that the factor, 'support system' which affects the adaptability towards the change from traditional to online is found high in both Non-Aided schools (71%), as well as in Urban Schools (71 %). Aided and Rural Schools have shown low scores on support systems with (40%) each. Support system affects all stakeholders to react towards online teaching- learning. It is responsible for high/low attitudes towards online teaching learning.

3.5 Motivation

Differences among government-aided, non-aided, rural, and urban schools regarding the factor of 'support system', affecting the adaptability towards the change.

Figure:3.5

The Motivation Factor Affecting the Adaptability Towards the Change

Interpretation:

Figure 3.5 indicates that the factor, 'motivation' which affects the adaptability towards the change from traditional to online, is found to be high in Non-Aided schools (81%), followed by Urban Schools (72%). Aided and Rural Schools have shown very low scores on motivation with (28%) and (21%) respectively. Motivation affects not only learners and teachers but also every stakeholder to react positively towards online teaching-learning.

3.6 Infrastructure:

Differences among government-aided, non-aided, rural, and urban schools regarding the factor 'Infrastructure', affecting the adaptability towards the change

Figure: 3.6
The Infrastructure factor affecting the adaptability towards the change

Interpretation

Figure 3.6 indicates that the factor, 'Infrastructure' which affects the adaptability towards the change from traditional to online is found high in Urban Schools (75%), followed by Non-aided schools (68%). Aided and Rural Schools have shown comparatively low scores on infrastructure with (51%) and (41%) respectively. Infrastructure affects learners to react towards online teaching-learning.

3.7 Communication:

Differences among government-aided, non-aided, rural, and urban schools regarding the factor of 'communication', affecting the adaptability towards the change

Figure 3.7
The Communication factor affecting the adaptability towards the change

The Communication factor affecting the adaptability towards the change

Interpretation:

Figure 3.7 indicates that the factor, 'communication' which affects the adaptability towards the change from traditional to online is found high in Urban Schools (85%), followed by Non-aided schools (81%). Aided and Rural Schools have shown very low scores on communication with (24%) and (34%) respectively. Communication plays a significant role for all stakeholders to react towards online teaching-learning.

4. To study the role of management and parents in providing facilities to improve teaching-learning.

Differences among government-aided, non-aided, rural, and urban schools regarding the role of management and parents providing facilities to improve teaching-learning.

Figure 4

The role of management and parents in providing facilities to improve teaching learning.

Interpretation:

In Figure 4, data indicates that to provide facilities to improve teaching-learning, the role of management and parents in government-aided schools, Non-aided schools, and rural and urban schools differ from one another. Parents of Non-aided schools and Urban schools (85%) seems to be more alert and performed active roles than that of Aided (37%) and Rural (22%) schools. Management of Non-aided Schools (73%) and Urban schools (68%) have shown a great role in providing facilities to improve online teaching-learning than that of aided schools (53%) and Rural schools (40%) respectively.

Result and Discussion Findings

1. A significant difference has been found between government-aided and non-aided schools regarding resources among all types of secondary schools. Compared to aided schools, non-aided schools seem to be more strengthened with resources like smart classrooms, internet speed facilities, and availability of computers. Rural schools are least empowered with these resources.
2. A significant difference has been found between government-aided and non-aided schools regarding the attitudes of different stakeholders. The attitudes of the teachers of Non-aided schools are more positive than those of aided and rural schools (Coman et. a l., 2020).
3. A significant difference has been found between government-aided and non-aided schools regarding other factors of adaptability towards online teaching-learning like

Technological literacy, Access to technology, Learning Style, Support system, Motivation, Infrastructure, and Communication.

4. A significant difference has been found between government-aided and non-aided schools regarding the facilities provided by schools and parents.

In the context of online teaching-learning, Non-aided schools are found rich in resources, high attitudes towards adaptability by all stakeholders and are found positive towards change contradictory to the research of Malambo (2013). This may be, because they (non-aided schools) can charge higher tuition fees since they are not subject to government regulations regarding fee structures. These higher fees can generate additional revenue that can be reinvested into the school for infrastructure development, teacher salaries, and educational materials. Sometimes Non-aided schools have the flexibility to engage in fundraising and seek donations from alumni, local businesses, and community members. This can result in additional financial support that government-aided and rural schools may not have access to.

Non-aided schools may have greater autonomy in deciding how to allocate their resources. They can prioritize spending on infrastructure, teaching staff, technology, and other resources based on their specific needs and goals. Non-aided schools are often located in urban or more affluent areas where there is a higher potential for financial support from the local community and businesses. In contrast, rural schools may struggle to attract resources due to their remote locations and limited economic opportunities. Non-aided schools may have more flexibility in terms of hiring, curriculum development, and resource procurement, allowing them to adapt to changing needs more rapidly.

All stakeholders of Non-aided schools may be more inclined to innovation in education. This cultural openness to trying new approaches can result in more positive attitudes toward online teaching and learning, which is seen as a modern and innovative educational method (Senthikumar et al.,2020). Students, parents and teachers of non-aided schools are generally from higher socio-economic backgrounds in comparison to government-aided schools. All are enjoying the resources needed for online teaching at home too. It makes it easy and comfortable to attach themselves in all activities regarding online teaching in comparison to government -aided or rural schools.

In India, mostly the students of government -aided schools are from lower-class or lower-middle class family. Education is not very important for them. They have to arrange their livelihood in very tough situations. So they do not want to spend anything on education of their wards. Even sometimes they do not want to send their children to schools because they engage them in either household activities or in help for their own earnings.

Parents in non-aided schools may be more involved in their children's education and more supportive of educational changes. They may actively participate in facilitating online learning and providing necessary resources at home. The stakeholders in non-aided schools may see online teaching and learning as aligned with their educational goals and values, such as flexibility, personalized learning, and adaptability to changing circumstances.

Positive attitudes regarding the perception that online teaching and learning are effective in achieving educational objectives motivate all stakeholders to adopt it. When teachers, students, and parents see tangible benefits and outcomes, they are more likely to support and embrace the approach. Non-aided schools may invest in professional development and training for their teachers to effectively use online teaching tools and methods. This can result in higher teacher confidence and better implementation (Muthuprasad et.al, 2021).

Online teaching and learning often require effective communication and collaboration between teachers, students, and parents. Non-aided schools may have systems in place to facilitate this, which can enhance the overall experience and imbibe positive attitudes. In non-aided schools, parents often choose the school based on their preferences and educational philosophies. This choice can lead to a more supportive and positive attitude toward the chosen method of instruction, including online learning.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that non-aided secondary schools are always more resourceful and successful in online teaching and learning compared to aided government schools. Non-aided schools may have advantages in certain areas related to online teaching and learning such as adaptability, availability of digital infrastructure, availability of devices and internet connectivity, leadership, and the dedication of its stakeholders, which play a significant role in shaping these attitudes. Non-aided schools may have more flexibility to provide additional training for their teachers in online pedagogy. Non-aided schools may have a more affluent or motivated parent community, which can provide better support for online learning initiatives.

Additionally, the success of online teaching and learning depends on effective implementation, ongoing support, and the alignment of technology with pedagogical goals. Non-aided schools are found to be more concerned and oriented towards online teaching.

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